

ENERGY TRANSITION OF FIBRE-BUNDLES AND THEIR UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES UNDER TENSILE IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The stress-strain curves of fibre-bundles or their composites under tensile impact always show nonlinear. It is irreversible and accompanied with energy dissipation. A perfect stress-strain curve is obtained from tensile impact. From this curve, the statistical strength of a single fibre can be reckoned, and the calculated data coincide with Weibull distribution. In the present paper, an infrared set-up to use for measuring the transient temperature of specimen was manufactured. The test results of GF, CF and GFRP are in agreement with the calculated data based on the energy dissipation to transform heat in an adiabatical process. The mechanism analysis shows the dissipation originates from broken fibres, the fracture of bundles is quasi-brittle and the failure of bundles is cumulative.

KEYWORDS: Bundles; Composites; Tensile impact; Dissipation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Recent years Kawata⁽¹⁾, Harding⁽²⁾, Xia⁽³⁾, Yang⁽⁴⁾ etc had done a great deal of tensile impact experimental studies for fibre reinforced polymers. Dong⁽⁵⁾ made successfully tensile impact tests of bundles (GF, CF, KF), and studied the rate-relativity of bundles from the tests. He obtained perfect stress-strain curves of bundles and their unidirectional composites. These curves are nonlinear, and show the loading process until fracture (Figure. 1).

FIGURE 1 Perfect stress-strain curve

According to the thermodynamic point of view, the total loading process of tensile impact is adiabatical and irreversible. In this process, both high-speed deformation and irreversible energy transition are taken place in the specimen. And the transient temperature is rising. This is caused by the mechanism of high-speed deformation. Hence, it is necessary to study the energy transition under tensile impact for founding a constitutive equation.

In this paper: energy analysis is made for perfect stress-strain curve obtained from tensile impact tests of fibre bundles and their unidirectional composites; formulae of dissipative energy and transient temperature rising in these tests are derived; and the variation of transient temperature of the specimen is measured by a self-designed infrared set-up. Comparing and demonstrating the measured and calculated values, the mechanism of these materials under tensile impact can be promulgated macroscopically.

2. BASIC THEORY

Classic statistical strength theory of fibre proposes hypotheses for bundles with length L , and fibre number N as the following:

- Initial status of every fibre is the same, i.e. length L and crossection A_f are same, and without initial stress.
- Fibre is linear and elastic until fracture, modulus E_f remains unchanged.
- The strength of fibre is regarded to obey the Weibull distribution.
- The stress in the unbroken fibres are equal when some fibres are breaking.

These hypotheses are extended from quasi-static loading to tensile impact, and from fibre to unidirectional composites. The composites are simplified to composed bundle model made up by N composed fibres with length L , and the composed fibre is made up by a single fibre surrounded by matrix. Then, the statistical analysis of the perfect stress-strain curve (Figure.1) under tensile impact can be carried on^(6,7).

From abovementioned hypotheses, the nonlinearity of the perfect stress-strain curve originates from cumulative fracture of fibres or composed fibres. If the number of broken fibres or composed fibres is n , and the moninal stress is σ_{BC} at point C (Figure.1), based on the hypotheses the true stress in the unbroken fibres or composed fibres is σ_{fc} , the resultant will be

$$P_c = \sigma_{fc} A_f (N - n). \quad (1)$$

But
$$\sigma_{BC} = \frac{P_c}{A_f N}, \quad (2)$$

then
$$\sigma_{BC} = \sigma_{fc} \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right), \quad (3)$$

and
$$\frac{n}{N} = 1 - \frac{\sigma_{BC}}{\sigma_{fc}}. \quad (4)$$

The strain energy stores in the unbroken fibres is

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{fc} \epsilon_c A_f L (N - n) \tag{5}$$

The strain energy density of specimen is

$$U = \frac{W}{A_f L N} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{fc} \epsilon_c \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right), \tag{6}$$

or
$$U = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{bc} \epsilon_c. \tag{7}$$

This is the area of triangle OCB. The work per unit volume of specimen made by loading force is

$$U^*(t) = \int_0^{\epsilon_c} \sigma(t) d\epsilon(t). \tag{8}$$

Obviously, $U^*(t) > U(t)$, Put $U_p(t) = U^*(t) - U(t)$, then

$$U_p(t) = \int_0^{\epsilon_c} \sigma(t) d\epsilon(t) - \frac{1}{2} \sigma_c(t) \epsilon_c(t). \tag{9}$$

$U_p(t)$ is the shadowed part of Figure 1. It is the irreversible energy of bundles or their unidirectional composites originated by the broken fibres or composed fibres under tensile impact, and $U(t)$ is the reversible energy.

According to Griffith theory, the crack extension force G equals to the surface energy density γ_s of crack for ideal brittle fracture. It means no energy dissipation. Recent studies show the deformation of some metals and glassy polymers (for example PMMA) is almost elastic until fracture, but $G > \gamma_s^{(8,9)}$, and a small irreversible deformation region happens near the crack tip. Quasi-brittle fracture is named to fracture of these materials, and $G = 2(\gamma_s + \gamma_p)$, $\gamma_p > \gamma_s$, where $2\gamma_p$ is dissipative energy to transform heat in the irreversible process.

Now, postulate the fracture of fibre or composed fibre is quasi-brittle, and $U_p(t)$ is released and transforms to heat entirely. As for adiabatical process.

$$T_p(t) = \frac{1}{J\rho C_p} U_p(t), \tag{10}$$

where $T_p(t)$ is the temperature variation, ρ density of material, J thermal equivalent of work, and C_p specific heat under fixed pressure.

Based on Kelvin's formula⁽¹⁰⁾ and above mentioned analysis, temperature variation caused by the elastic deformation of unbroken fibres or composed fibres can be derived

$$T_e(t) = -T_0 \left\{ 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\lambda\sigma(t)}{J\rho C_p}\right] \right\} \quad (11)$$

where T_0 — environment temperature of specimen, λ —expansion coefficient. At last, the calculating formula of theoretical temperature variation $T^*(t)$ of bundles or their unidirectional composites under tensile impact is

$$T^*(t) = -T_0 \left\{ 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\lambda\sigma(t)}{J\rho C_p}\right] \right\} + \frac{1}{J\rho C_p} \left[\int_0^{\sigma(t)} \sigma(t) d\varepsilon(t) - \frac{1}{2} \sigma(t) \varepsilon(t) \right] \quad (12)$$

From eqn(9) and (12), perfect stress-strain curve and relevant material constants, the theoretical values $U_p(t)$ and $T^*(t)$ can be determined easily.

3. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

To verify eqn(12), it is necessary to obtain perfect stress-strain curve and transient temperature variation $T(t)$ of specimen in the same time while it is loaded with tensile impact.

3-1 Experiment and measurement Tensile impact test is carried out on a self-designed bar-to-bar impact set-up with a pendulum. The set-up, specimen and its installation are shown in ref.[11]. Figure 2 is a scheme of this system. When the pendulum impacts the block, the short elastic-plastic metal bar breaks. Then an approximate rectangular stress impulse propagates through input bar and specimen to output bar. We get incident wave $\varepsilon_i(t)$ from strain gauge on input bar, and transient wave $\varepsilon_t(t)$ from gauge on output bar. Based on the experimental principle, $\sigma(t)$, $\varepsilon(t)$, $\dot{\varepsilon}(t)$ and the perfect stress-strain curve can be obtained easily.

FIGURE 2 Scheme of impact set-up

An infrared radiant method is used for measuring the transient temperature variation. The measuring set-up is self-designed (Figure 3) with a frequency bandwidth $\Delta f = 200 \sim 10^7$ Hz, and a temperature distinguishability 0.5°C . The principle and design of this set-up are shown in ref.[12]. In Figure 2 and Figure 3, the wavestorage is multiway. Therefore, the measured $\sigma(t)$, $\epsilon(t)$ and $T(t)$ are isochronic.

FIGURE 3 Scheme of infrared set-up

Using this set-up (Figure 3), one measures and gets the average temperature variation $T(t)$ of an arbitrary small region on specimen at a fixed position. When the specimen is multi-bundles or unidirectional composite made of many fibres or composed fibres, the broken part of fibres or composed fibres in specimen is uniform in random way. Hence, the temperature variation of specimen is uniform statistically. Then, the measured average temperature variation of multibundles or unidirectional composites under tensile impact can be considered as the temperature variation in a macroscopic sense on specimen.

3-2 Experimental and measuring results

FIGURE 4 Results of GF

FIGURE 5 Results of CF

Figure 4 illustrates the experimental and measuring results of GF, and Figure 5 is of CF. From Figure 4, the temperature of specimen decreases as stress-strain curve is linear, and the temperature increases as stress-strain curve deviates from linearity. When the stress is maximum, temperature increases rapidly, and when the stress reduces to zero, the temperature reaches maximum. For CF, the results are same, but the temperature keeps unchanged before the deviation of linearity of stress-strain curve. Therefore, at the initial loading stage, it lacks of dissipation to GF and CF. Additionally, because the thermal expansion coefficient $\alpha_{GF} > 0$ for GF, and $\alpha_{CF} \approx 0$ for CF, the temperature variation at the initial stage of GF and CF are decreasing or remain unchanged respectively. While some fibres are breaking, heat is released. It means the fracture of fibre is not ideal brittle fracture. At least, breaking of fibre is an important reason to cause temperature rising.

The experimental and measuring results of unidirectional GFRP are shown in Figure 6. During the total tensile impact loading, temperature variation of GFRP is just as that of GF.

FIGURE 6 Results of GFRP

The temperature rising curve $T(t)$ measured for GF and GFRP, as well as the theoretical curves $T^*(t)$ calculated from eqn(12) are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. $T(t)$ and $T^*(t)$ are accordant. And the results of CF are also accordant.

FIGURE 7 Temperature rising curve of GF

FIGURE 8 Temperature rising curve of GFRP

4. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

(1) the transient temperature rising curve $T(t)$ measured under tensile impact of bundles and their unidirectional composites agree with the theoretical temperature rising curve $T^*(t)$ calculated from eqn(12). It means the analysis of energy transition of these materials under tensile impact is correct. Owing to the analysis is based on above mentioned hypotheses, i.e. the hypothesis of classical statistical strength theory of fibres, the hypothesis of composed fibre model, and the hypothesis of quasi-brittle fracture of fibre, the conformability of $T(t)$ and $T^*(t)$ means these hypotheses are correct.

(2) According to the energy analysis and experimental results, it puts forward a preliminary frame to characterize the mechanical behaviors of unidirectional composites under tensile impact and to propose a constitutive model under high strain rate. The main points of the frame are:

- Nonlinearity of stress-strain curve is caused by the cumulative fracture of composed fibres.
- The unloading line from points C (Figure 1) follows CO.
- The shadowed part (Figure 1) equals to the dissipative energy of the fracture of composed fibres.

The foundation of above mentioned points is linear elastic composed fibres and the statistical property of their strength. Hence, as long as the point of view of micromechanics is hold, the rate relativity of fibre and matrix is guided in the statistical strength theory of composites under quasi-static loading, it is possible to find a statistical constitutive model of composites consisted of rate relativity.

(3) According to ref.[8,9] and the present paper, it is possible to predict the existence of a small irreversible deformed region near the fracture of GF or CF. This region may look on as a microscopic point, the temperature rising in this region is far greater than the macroscopic temperature rising. According to ref.[9], the temperature in this region may be greater than the glass transition temperature. Then, plastic yielding happens on this micropoint. Plainly, it is impossible to influence the stress-strain curve. But it is worth to do further study of this problem from both micro- and macroscopic point of view.

(4) The energy analysis and transient measurement of temperature of the present paper provide a physical foundation for the study of the mechanism of composites. It is an effective way to study the constitutive relation and rupture theory of composites.

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BIOGRAPHY

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